

D3.2

BEERi activity report

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Deliverable abstract

The BEERi activity report summarizes the activities of the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructure (BEERi) within the lifetime of the ENVRI-FAIR project. It provides an overview of the main common topics tackled within the BEERi and taken actions regarding them, illustrating the cooperation of the Community of the environmental RIs.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D3.2 – BEERi activity report

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The ENVRI Community is overseen and strategically led by the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures (BEERi) which works on common strategies, positions, policies and participations (see Table 1). BEERi was established in the beginning of the ENVRIplus project in 2015 and has continued its activities on a regular basis throughout the ENVRI-FAIR project.

The objective of the BEERi is to engage the ENVRI cluster, discuss on the strategy and vision of the RIs belonging to the four environmental domains (life, air, land, water), share knowledge and support RIs at different maturity levels, develop joint solutions and formulate common messages and recommendations towards various stakeholders (EC, ESFRI, other science clusters, general public, etc.). BEERi acts as a forum to strengthen the unified voice of the ENVRI RIs as the environmental RIs are connected to each other through similar challenges in their planning, design as well as in their operations.

The BEERi work was facilitated by the ENVRI-FAIR WP3 that took care of organizing the BEERi meetings, preparing the meeting agendas and meeting materials in collaboration with the BEERi chair and the vice-chair, putting together the meeting minutes and following the implementation of agreed action points after the BEERi meetings and by ensuring the regular communication within BEERi members via a dedicated BEERi email list.

Throughout the ENVRI-FAIR years, BEERi has met regularly, at least twice a year, during the BEERi meetings organized within ENVRI weeks or in independent BEERi meetings.

Table 1. BEERi in a nutshell.

BEERi – Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures

- **Consists of RI directors or coordinators from the environmental domain research infrastructures**
 - **Includes currently 26 RIs as BEERi members (each RI has max 2 representatives)**
 - **Aims at formulating common strategies, positions, policies and participations**
 - **Meets regularly - at least twice a year**
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1.2 Composition of BEERi

At present, the BEERi consists of 26 RIs (ESFRI landmarks and projects as well as other networks and communities established outside ESFRI or on the way to become RIs in the environmental domain). Each RI has up to two representatives in the BEERi. The BEERi representatives are named by the RIs themselves and are typically the directors or coordinators of the RIs.

The current composition of the BEERi in alphabetical order is: ACTRIS, AnaEE, AQUACOSM-plus, ARISE, CETAF, DANUBIUS-RI, EISCAT-3D, eLTER, EMBRC, EMPHASIS, EMSO, EPOS, EUFAR, Euro-Argo, EUROFLEETSplus, EuroGOOS, GROOMII, HEMERA RI, IAGOS, ICOS, INTERACT, IS-ENES3, JERICO-RI, LifeWatch, SeaDataNet and SIOS.

During the lifespan of ENVRI-FAIR, BEERi was chaired by three different chairs (two female chairs and one male chair). Sanna Sorvari Sundet, who acted as the BEERi chair from the beginning of ENVRIplus, continued in the role in ENVRI-FAIR during the period January 2019 – November 2019. In November 2019, Ingrid Puillat was elected as the BEERi chair, and in February 2020, Werner Kutsch was selected as the BEERi vice-chair. In June 2022, Werner Kutsch was appointed as the chair of BEERi and Helen Glaves as the vice-chair of BEERi for a mandate that will run until the end of 2023.

1.3 Purpose of the BEERi activity report

The purpose of this report is to sum up the work and activities of the BEERi during the ENVRI-FAIR project lifetime (01.01.2019-30.06.2023). The key focus of the summary is on the BEERi meetings and main topics discussed in the meetings, as well as on the common actions taken to elaborate the cluster work, face the requests and demands of the stakeholders and society and enhance the voice and position of the environmental RIs.

2 BEERi activities during ENVRI-FAIR

2.1 BEERi meetings

The BEERi work has taken shape around the regular BEERi meetings, which have been prepared based on the actual topics and e.g., requests from the European Commission, ESFRI, society, initiatives outside ENVRI Community, different events where ENVRI is represented, etc. Between the BEERi meetings, communication with the BEERi members has been handled through a dedicated BEERi email list. A summary of the BEERi meetings held during the ENVRI-FAIR and the essential topics discussed in these meetings is given in Table 2.

During the lifetime of the ENVRI-FAIR project, altogether 19 BEERi meetings were organized (6 meetings in the 1st reporting period, 4 meetings in the 2nd reporting period and 9 meetings in the 3rd reporting period). Due to the COVID19-pandemic, most of the BEERi meetings were organized in virtual mode. Usually the in-person meetings were organized during the ENVRI weeks, which enabled important discussions with the whole ENVRI Community and reflections on the ENVRI-FAIR project progress and outcomes relevant for the BEERi.

In addition to actual BEERi meetings, BEERi members have been actively representing the ENVRI Community in various meetings, events, and forums throughout the ENVRI-FAIR project.

2.2 Main topics of the BEERi work

Typically, the topics discussed in the BEERi meetings included a wide range of different short- and long-term issues. However, some of the BEERi meetings were dedicated solely to one or two topics, for example due to a need for formulation of a common response on behalf of the ENVRI Community for a specific audience. The key topics of the BEERi meetings are presented in Table 2.

During the 1st reporting period of ENVRI-FAIR (01.01.2019-30.06.2020), altogether 6 BEERi meetings were arranged: physical meetings in Prague (January 2019), Helsinki (March 2019), Brussels (June 2019), Amsterdam (November 2019) and Dresden (February 2020), and one virtual meeting in May 2020. In the beginning of the first reporting period, the list of BEERi members was updated (January 2019). In the BEERi meetings, the BEERi tackled especially the ENVRI strategy and governance theme by focusing on five categories: Visibility and communication (1), Fragmented funding landscape (2), Positioning of RIs (3), Collaboration of RIs (4), and Organisational structure (5). BEERi discussed and prepared the ENVRI response to the COVID-19 outbreak by pointing that environmental RIs can support the understanding the environmental conditions which favor the evolution of a pandemic, particularly when related to a warming climate, changes in ecosystems or biodiversity losses.

In addition, BEERi discussed the involvement of ENVRI in EOSC related calls and initiatives. The ENVRI visibility and communication activities, the ENVRI input to Horizon Europe Missions, and the

means to improve RI collaboration were also shared discussion topics in the BEERi meetings until mid-2020.

Within the second reporting period (01.07.2020 – 31.12.2021), 4 BEERi meetings in total were held: in December 2020, February 2021, June 2021, and November 2021. All of the meetings were organized virtually. One main topic of these meetings was the formulation of the ENVRI Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) and the Terms of Reference (ToR). The objective of the MoU is to facilitate cooperation and to provide and advocate a common vision of the European Research Infrastructures in the field of environmental sciences. As for the related ToR, they define the general governance structure of the ENVRI Community necessary to achieve the implementation of the goals expressed in the MoU. Another important theme within the BEERi during the second reporting period was putting together a common ENVRI statement to the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aiming at engaging in a dialogue with the European Commission on the upcoming Framework Programme.

The ENVRI participation in EC funded calls and projects as well as in EOSC related activities were also covered. From the communications perspective, the ENVRI visibility and rebranding and the ENVRI communications strategy was worked upon among the BEERi members. The purpose of the BEERi was revisited and Working Groups on BEERi/ENVRI relevant topics were established, aiming to ease and structure the BEERi work better.

During the third and last reporting period (01.01.2022 – 30.06.2023), altogether 9 BEERi meetings were held: in February 2022, March 2022 (two separate meetings), April 2022, June 2022, July 2022, August 2022, November 2022, and February 2023. All of these meetings, except the last one, were organized virtually. The last BEERi meeting during the last reporting period was held as a hybrid meeting in junction with the ENVRI week 2023 in Leipzig. Within the last period, most of the BEERi meetings were short, dedicated meetings concentrating on single topics which required brainstorming and shaping of a joint approach. BEERi prepared common thoughts for the workshop on the R&I needs of Research Infrastructures in the next Horizon Europe rounds that was organized by the European Commission and ESFRI. As a follow-up of the R&I needs meeting, BEERi formulated later again a common input for a meeting with the Commission.

Apart from these missions, BEERi put together an ENVRI position paper on the request of the European Commission, to identify challenges on the way to an improved European landscape of environmental Research Infrastructures. In the end of the third reporting period, BEERi worked on formulating an endorsement form for initiatives that are interested to receive an ENVRI/BEERi endorsement for their proposals.

In addition to the focal topics of the individual BEERi meetings (presented in Table 2), the BEERi has discussed on a regular basis on several other topics such as the progress and the activities of the ENVRI-FAIR project relevant for the BEERi, EOSC news and developments, ENVRI RIs involvement and strategy in calls and proposals, new BEERi member applications, ERIC Forum updates, ENVRI participation and visibility in events and meetings (e.g. recurring big events such as EGU, AGU, ICRI, etc.), and the development of the ENVRI communications activities. In addition, news and updates from the ENVRI RIs have been shared and discussed as an established practice at the beginning of each BEERi meeting.

Table 2. BEERi meetings held and key topics discussed within the meetings during the ENVRI-FAIR project (January 2019 – June 2023).

BEERi meeting number (since the board was established in 2015)	Main agenda topics	Meeting type (physical/virtual), place and time
9 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on ENVRIplus final results and ENVRI-FAIR kick-off outcomes and next activities • Planning of ENVRIplus Dissemination event in Brussels • Follow-up and hands-on working on action items on ENVRI sustainability and strategy agreed in Riga workshop (Nov 2018) 	Physical meeting, Prague, January 2019
10 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on ENVRI sustainability and strategy • Planning of ENVRIplus Dissemination event • Discussion on ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC initiatives 	Physical meeting, Helsinki, March 2019
11 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on ENVRIplus deliverables related to ENVRI sustainability, strategy and landscape analysis • Nomination and selection process for a new BEERi chair 	Physical meeting, Brussels, June 2019
12 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on organizational position of BEERi, BEERi Terms of Reference (ToR), and Criteria of the BEERi membership • Selection of new BEERi chair • ENVRI landscape illustration 	Physical meeting, Amsterdam, November 2019
13 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approval of the BEERi Deputy Chair • ENVRI strategy and governance • Discussion towards a common ENVRI statement on Horizon Europe 	Physical meeting, Dresden, February 2020
14 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENVRI input to Horizon Europe Missions • ENVRI community response to COVID-19 	Virtual meeting, May 2020
15 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENVRI community MoU and ToR • ENVRI statement to the Horizon Europe Framework Programme • Discussion on communications strategy for ENVRI community 	Virtual meeting, December 2020
16 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key 2021 actions for the BEERi and the ENVRI Community in domains and across domains • Implementation of the ENVRI communications strateg 	Virtual meeting, February 2021

BEERi meeting number (since the board was established in 2015)	Main agenda topics	Meeting type (physical/virtual), place and time
17 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENVRI Community MoU process • Discussion and Q/A on recently published white papers related to international collaboration on RIs 	Virtual meeting, June 2021
18 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting up Working Groups for BEERi/ENVRI relevant topics • ENVRI rebranding and revamp of the community website 	Virtual meeting, November 2021
19 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on BEERi chair and deputy chair election process • Discussion on ENVRI representative for the ERIC Forum Executive Board • Identifying and prioritizing BEERi Working Groups • Revisiting the ENVRI Vision and Mission statements 	Virtual meeting, February 2022
20 th BEERi meeting	Voting meeting on the BEERi Chairperson and the ENVRI representative in the Executive Board of the ERIC FORUM	Virtual meeting, 10 th March 2022
21 st BEERi meeting	Meeting on the preparation for the workshop on the needs of Research Infrastructures in the next HE rounds	Virtual meeting, 28 th March 2022
22 nd BEERi meeting	Meeting on common ENVRI input to ESFRI Landscape analysis workshop	Virtual meeting, April 2022
23 rd BEERi meeting	Meeting on BEERi chair and vice chair election	Virtual meeting, June 2022
24 th BEERi meeting	A preparation meeting to collect common input for the discussion points of the meeting with the Commission (to be held later in July 2022)	Virtual meeting, July 2022
25 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on Position paper of the ENVRI Community (addressing some specific challenges on the way to an improved European landscape of environmental Research Infrastructures) 	Virtual meeting, August 2022
26 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERIC Forum updates • Review of the final version of the ENVRI Position paper • ENVRI and forthcoming opportunities 	Virtual meeting, November 2022
27 th BEERi meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlights of ENVRI week 2023 • Discussion on ENVRI/BEERi endorsement on new initiatives and proposals • Working session of the BEERi Working Groups • Revisit of ENVRI MoU • ENVRI-FAIR Final event planning 	Hybrid meeting, Leipzig/Online, February 2023

3 Conclusions

The Board of Environmental Research Infrastructures has worked regularly during the ENVRI-FAIR. The COVID-19 pandemic changed the working habits of the board towards remote meetings. The number of BEERi meetings was increased during the pandemic compared to the time before the outbreak because the opportunities for BEERi members to meet in person were drastically reduced.

As a summary, some main outcomes of the BEERi activity (or activity where BEERi members have contributed) include:

- [ENVRI Community response to COVID-19](#)
- [ENVRI Community statement to the Horizon Europe Framework Programme](#)
- Recommendations by the ENVRI Community (ENVRI Position paper) to address some specific challenges on the way to an improved European landscape of environmental Research Infrastructures (RIs)
- Endorsement form for initiatives seeking ENVRI/BEERi endorsement for their proposals
- ENVRI Cluster response to ESFRI Landscape Analysis Questionnaire
- Triggered participation of ENVRI in responding to several calls in Horizon Europe in the INFRA work program
- Minutes from all BEERi meetings that gather main discussions and agreed action points